

MEDICAL SCIENCE

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MODERN CONCEPTS OF COMPREHENSIVE TREATMENT IN ORTHODONTICS

Abstract

Orthodontics is a branch of dentistry that studies the development of the maxillofacial region, the formation of occlusion, and the dentoalveolar system as a whole. It also involves the diagnosis, prevention, and treatment of occlusion anomalies.

Modern orthodontics addresses the following tasks:

- *Study of factors leading to the development of dentoalveolar and maxillofacial anomalies;*
- *Examination of the pathogenesis of dentoalveolar anomalies;*
- *Development of new diagnostic methods;*
- *Creation of preventive and treatment methods for dentoalveolar and maxillofacial anomalies and occlusal deformities;*
- *Development of preventive and treatment methods for defects of individual teeth, dental arches, jaws, and facial structures in children;*
- *Elimination of factors contributing to the development of dentoalveolar and maxillofacial anomalies.*

Keywords: *orthodontics, treatment methods, dentoalveolar anomalies, orthodontic appliances, bracket systems.*

Preventive orthodontics is a set of measures aimed at preventing and eliminating the etiological and pathogenetic factors that lead to the development of dentoalveolar and maxillofacial anomalies. Many scientists have addressed orthodontic treatment issues in dentistry. For example, F.Ya. Khoroshilkina identified six directions in orthodontics based on the age of patients requiring treatment and the specifics of therapeutic interventions:

1. Preventive orthodontics among organized children's groups.
2. Specialized treatment for children in orthodontic clinics or departments.
3. Orthodontic treatment for adolescents.
4. Orthodontic treatment for adults.
5. Orthodontic treatment and dentoalveolar prosthetics for patients with congenital developmental defects (cleft lip, alveolar process defects, and cleft palate) within their complex treatment.
6. Orthodontic treatment in surgical inpatient settings as a preparatory or final stage of surgical-reconstructive correction of dentoalveolar and maxillofacial anomalies and occlusal deformities.

The question of orthodontic treatment for adults is ambiguous. In cases where the dental arches are intact, many adult patients with bite anomalies can still chew food satisfactorily. For this reason, adults do not always seek orthodontic help unless aesthetics are affected.

The situation changes when teeth are extracted, as the clinical picture shifts significantly. In this case, the pathology typical of anomalies is compounded by

symptoms associated with partial tooth loss. This results in not just a simple summation of symptoms, but the emergence of new, qualitatively different signs. For instance, a deep bite may become a traumatic bite after tooth loss. Prosthetic treatment for such patients presents significant challenges and is often impossible without special preparation [1].

The treatment of dentoalveolar anomalies in adults has its own specifics, which are influenced by several factors:

1. Orthodontic treatment is performed when the formation of the facial skeleton is already complete;
2. Bone tissue is less pliable and more difficult to reshape under the influence of orthodontic appliances;
3. The adaptability to appliances in adults is significantly lower than in children;
4. Dentoalveolar anomalies are worsened by defects and deformities in the dental arches;
5. Orthodontic treatment is more prolonged.

These factors explain why recurrences of anomalies are more common after orthodontic treatment in adults.

Considering the limited possibilities of orthodontic treatment for dentoalveolar anomalies in adults, prosthetic treatment should be applied more widely. General indications for this approach can include the following: patient refusal of surgical treatment or the presence of contraindications to it. The latter can include chronic systemic diseases, specific psychological status, advanced age, the absence of a large number of teeth, or a completely edentulous jaw.

When determining the indications for orthodontic treatment in adults, the patient's ability to maintain oral hygiene at an appropriate level is of great importance. It is also necessary to consider that an adult patient may have fixed partial dentures, and if they are metal-ceramic, there are no issues with the fixation of orthodontic brackets. However, if the dentures are metal and their position and inclination are unfavorable, it is better to remove them.

Orthodontic treatment in adults should also take into account potential problems with the temporomandibular joints. Nevertheless, despite all of the above, orthodontic treatment in the presence of periodontitis can significantly contribute to the elimination of an imbalanced occlusion, which in turn leads to the resolution of the inflammatory process.

Naturally, orthodontic treatment should be followed by prosthetics when necessary. In the case of periodontal diseases in adults, the approach to orthodontic treatment should be very cautious, limited to early stages and using light forces from the appliances. The orthodontic forces applied to the teeth should be as weak as possible, achieved through the use of removable appliances with active elements made from 0.6 mm wire, as well as the use of the edgewise technique. After the completion of orthodontic tooth movement, they must be splinted to prevent relapse, occlusography should be performed, and selective grinding carried out if needed [3].

Various methods are used for the prevention and treatment of anomalies:

- Biological or functional.
- Orthodontic or appliance-based.
- Appliance-surgical.
- Surgical.

Biological methods for correcting anomalies include myogymnastics, but their primary role is prevention. This method is effective in preschool and school-age children. The appliance-based method of correcting anomalies involves the use of orthodontic appliances to modify the relationship of the dental arches, their shape, and the position of individual or groups of teeth. This method is most effective in children and adolescents. The appliance-surgical method is recommended for adults, i.e., when the duration of appliance-based treatment is prolonged or ineffective. Surgical methods are indicated when organ reconstruction is required, often involving dissection or plastic surgery, which cannot be achieved using orthodontic appliances alone.

Surgical treatment can only be applied after the growth of the jaws has finished. Among the surgical techniques that complement orthodontic treatment, the following have become widespread: removal of primary and permanent teeth, corticotomy, wedge-shaped resection of the alveolar ridge, decortication, and weakening of the interalveolar septa [2].

The adult population represents a significant portion of those in need of orthodontic treatment. While orthodontic treatment is undoubtedly beneficial for overall oral health, the most obvious advantage of this therapy is cosmetic correction. However, it is important to remember that people with orthodontic problems are much more likely to suffer from periodontal diseases,

TMJ disorders, headaches, neck, shoulder, and back pain—issues that can be prevented with proper treatment. Unfortunately, adult patients often experience doubts before starting orthodontic intervention and tend to avoid it due to insecurities related to wearing braces.

For a long time, the extended duration of treatment and the unattractive appearance of braces discouraged patients. As a result, a large number of adults have lived with existing aesthetic and oral health problems. Additionally, orthodontics is a specialized field, and many other dentists are cautious about providing orthodontic consultations or starting treatment. After discussing all alternatives with the patient, the appropriate treatment method is chosen to create an aesthetic smile, including "instant" (e.g., restorative) orthodontics. When patients learn about minimally invasive interventions, they often prefer to preserve the natural tooth structure rather than opt for veneers or other restorations. However, some orthodontic techniques that are more attractive to patients than braces (such as aligners) do not guarantee results [4].

Short-term orthodontics breaks down the barriers that previously prevented many patients from wearing braces. This technique is better accepted by patients and allows dentists to offer solutions for correcting minor defects rather than addressing significant issues according to Angle's classification. Short-term orthodontic treatment is an excellent foundation for enhancing the smile's aesthetics in individuals with fully formed jaws and bites that require minimal correction. Unlike standard methods, short-term orthodontic treatment allows most patients to achieve a perfect smile in just 6 months.

This concept is appealing due to its shorter treatment time, comfort, and aesthetic acceptability. As a result, all the negative aspects associated with traditional braces treatment are eliminated. Moreover, many people who wish to improve the aesthetics and health of their oral cavity often lack the financial means to undergo conventional orthodontic treatment. As a result, many patients simply avoid seeking help and neglect both their oral health and aesthetics. Since treatment expectations and outcomes are always discussed in detail with the patient, some may prioritize cost over the advantages of treatment.

Short-term orthodontic treatment is primarily designed to move teeth into the appropriate position for cosmetic correction rather than addressing all minor imperfections. By simply repositioning teeth according to facial proportions, overall symmetry and good results can be achieved. At the same time, many patients feel confident about the outcome only when wearing braces, as they struggle with the aesthetic concerns associated with their appearance.

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